

4TU.ResearchData & The Community

Connie Clare

Community Manager

c.e.clare@tudelft.nl

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Essentials 4 Data Support, RDNL

In this session we will cover:

- ✓ Data repository
- ✓ Partnership
- ✓ Technical features
- ✓ FAIR data challenges

- ✓ Community for support
- ✓ Data Stewards
- ✓ Plans & programming
- ✓ Reward & recognition

What is 4TU.ResearchData ?

SCIENCE • ENGINEERING • DESIGN

- International data repository
<https://data.4tu.nl/portal>

Science

Engineering

Design

- Available to researchers globally
- Founded in 2010

Sharing

Curation

Access

Preservation

4TU.Federation

Tailored discipline-specific solutions for FAIR data

Mathematics	Physics	Chemistry	Earth Sciences	Atmospheric Sciences
Physical Geography and Environmental Geoscience	Geomatic Engineering	Environmental Sciences	Biology	Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences
Information and Computing Sciences	Nanotechnology	Aerospace Engineering	Civil Engineering	Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Built Environment and Design	Materials Engineering	Mechanical Engineering	Medical and Health Sciences	Business and Management

- Atmospheric science (3321 datasets)
- Geomatic engineering (3213 datasets)
- Climate change (3211 datasets)

Deposits are assigned a DOI for linking and findability

Data publication and citation increases impact and visibility

Restricted access (embargo) for confidential data

Personal service of metadata and data review (tick box, QC)

Need help?

GitHub/GitLab integration for publishing versions of code

Technical solution for...

F_{indable} A_{ccessible} I_{nteroperable} R_{eusable}

Source: FAIR data principles under licence

Usage-statistics:
Views,
Downloads
Citations

Trusted, safe and secure, long-term preservation of research data

Achieving FAIR data: A researcher's perspective

Challenges:

- Lack of time
- Lack of incentive
- Administrative burden
- My data is not valuable
- Fear of scooping
- Personal/commercial data
- Lack of awareness
- Overwhelmed

Benefits:

- Safe & secure data preservation – no loss!
- Link to share with others – transparency
- Less wasted time, resources (& careers!)
- Opportunities for collaboration
- Improved verification, integrity
- Reproducibility
- Increased data reuse
- Compliance with policy requirements
- Less retractions of publications
- No more email requests!
- Views, download & citation metrics

Need for seamless services and human infrastructure!

Good infrastructure on its own won't make more data FAIR.

We need to work with the **communities**.

Proper data management is a prerequisite to Open Science

is a requirement of funders, journals, institutions & policies

Researchers may not know about the latest tools, services, policies & regulations

Diverse & large research-intensive institutions makes driving the cultural change difficult

Research communities and disciplinary problems cross institutional borders. We should collaborate in solving them.

The 4TU.ResearchData Community

 Aims to provide an **inclusive space** for members to **connect** and **exchange knowledge** about the best practices for creating and reusing **FAIR data**.

Plans & Programming

Discipline-specific
expertise

20x Data Stewards
OSCs
DCC

Consultancy

Partners, Gold, Silver,
Bronze members

Engagement & Education

Working groups
Workshops/training
Community calls

Community

Est. October 2020

Fellowship
programme

Recruit fellows for FAIR
data projects

Reward & Recognition

Online platform
Slack community
Researcher stories
Monthly newsletter

FAIR Data Funds

Budget for
making data FAIR
Spring/Fall

Aim: Capitalise on the diverse & multidisciplinary skillset!

Yan Wang
Coordinator
RDM ecosystem

Kees den Heijer
Civil Engineering &
Geosciences

Santosh Ilamparuthi
Electrical Engineering,
Mathematics &
Computer Science
Privacy & GDPR

Yasemin Türkyilmaz
Mechanical, Maritime
& Materials Engineering
Disciplinary guidance
for RDM

Diana Popa
Architecture & the
Built Environment
Personal data, ethics

Nicolas Dintzner
Technology, Policy
& Management
Open source

Heather Andrews
Aerospace Engineering

Jeff Love
Industrial Design
Engineering
Sharing qualitative
data

Esther Plomp
Applied Sciences
Open Scholarship

Qian Zhang
Coordinator
Behavioral & Social
Sciences,
Geoinformation & Earth
Observation
Personal data

Marianna Avetisyan
Electrical Engineering,
Mathematics &
Computer Science

Simone Fricke
Engineering/
Science Technology
Policy implementation

Judith Brands
Information Specialist,
TechMed Center
RDM education

Zafer Ozturk
FAIR awareness

Sjöf Öllers
Built Environment,
Chemistry
Privacy & GDPR

Sil van Lieshout
Mechanical Engineering,
Applied Physics,
Electrical Engineering
Reproducible code

Anne Aarts
Biomedical engineering,
Industrial design

Chiara Gallese Nobile
Privacy, GDPR, IPR

Phuong Truong
Reproducible code

Floor Luub
Mathematics & Computer
Science
Policy implementation,
GDPR

Community working groups (monthly)

You're an Organizer

4TU.RESEARCHDATA
DATA STEWARDS

Private / Group

 +15 members

You're an Organizer

FAIR AND
REPRODUCIBLE CODE
WORKING GROUP

Private / Group

 +15 members

You're an Organizer

PRIVACY AND GDPR
WORKING GROUP

Private / Group

 +14 members

You're an Organizer

ENGAGEMENT AND
EDUCATION WORKING
GROUP

Private / Group

 +13 members

- Match-making
- Exchange ideas, knowledge, best practices
- Co-creation

- Tools, training
- The Carpentries
- Licensing
- Version control
- Train the trainer/
Templates

- Sensitive data
- Informed consent
- Legal, ethical
- Inventory of data agreements (DPA, DTA, DAC, etc.)

- RDM courses
- Generic/disciplinary
- Resources, activities, games
- Disciplinary use cases

Webinars: Community Call

Building a Culture of Collaboration

The first Community Call
Friday, 30 April 2021
10:30-11:30 CET

- 1 hour long
- Intro to community
- Updates from WGs
- Guest speaker, **Malvika Sharan**

Next event in **October**

<http://bit.ly/CultureofCollaboration>

The community (Platform and Slack)

Almost 70 online members

<https://community.data.4tu.nl/>

The screenshot shows the 4TU ResearchData website with a navigation bar (BLOG, GET INVOLVED, NEWS & EVENTS, ABOUT) and a user profile (CONNIE CLARE). The main content features a call for a community event: 'Attend our first Community Call: Building a Culture of Collaboration'. The event is a workshop on 'Software Carpentry' for MOOC Open Science, held from May 19 to June 23, 2021. The workshop is a four-afternoon event for PhD candidates, focusing on reproducibility and productivity in research. The event is presented by Anna Westland on March 31, 2021. A video player for '4TU ResearchData' is also visible, along with social media links and a members list.

Reward & recognition for data

Impact & visibility for members

Connections between stakeholders

Public presence to inform and inspire

Blog

- Researcher stories
- Research support
- Collaborations

Get involved:

- Working groups
- FAIR Data Funds

News & Events

- Newsletter archive
- Upcoming events
- Event highlights

About

- Community members
- 4TU.ResearchData

Monthly round-up from 4TU.ResearchData

The Easter vacation is just around the corner and we have a spring in our step!

The March edition of our newsletter from 4TU.ResearchData is full of stories about community members and includes the top downloaded datasets from the last month!

News

Making OperationAIR data FAIR

As nations around the world mark a year since the first lockdown, TU Delft Technical Medicine Master's students, [Tom Dijkhuis](#) and [Max Ligtenberg](#), reflect on the success of the OperationAIR project.

We met Tom and Max to learn how they used last year's [Data Refinement Fund](#) from 4TU.ResearchData to make their AIRone Covid-19 ventilator data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

[Read their story](#) and [view their dataset!](#)

Flower Power! A tool for automated plant identification

RDNL Dutch Data Prize winner and PhD student from the [University of Twente](#), [Diah Harmoni Apriyanti](#), shares [the story behind her orchid flowers dataset](#) and her motivations for making her data and code openly available online.

Congratulations to Diah!

Researcher stories

Development of a Data Access Committee

TU Delft Data Steward from the faculty of [Electrical Engineering Mathematics and Computer Science \(EEMCS\)](#), [Santosh Ilamparuthi](#), has developed a Data Access Committee to control access to data published under 'restricted access' in the 4TU.ResearchData repository.

Santosh presented [his pilot initiative](#) during a [Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences Data Steward Interest group](#) meeting on 8th March.

Research support

A new repository feature!

Software publishing made easier: An integration between 4TU.ResearchData and GitLab

Software development work is currently underway to integrate the [4TU.ResearchData repository](#) with [GitLab](#), an open-source DevOps tool used for collaborative and transparent working among research groups.

[Read more about this new feature coming soon in 2021!](#)

Features & updates

Opportunities

New Vacancy: Developer of Open Science Data Infrastructures

Join the team at 4TU.ResearchData as a developer to help shape the future of scholarly communication infrastructure! If you're passionate about open source and developing infrastructures to help researchers share their results then this position is for you.

[Apply by 10th April.](#)

Vacancies & invitations

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE.

Calling researchers at the University of Twente!

Are you looking for flexible, efficient and scalable computing infrastructure to perform complex simulations and calculations?

[Apply to use the Virtual Research Environment \(VRE\)!](#)

Provided by [Library, ICT services and Archive \(LISA\)](#), the VRE offers researchers an easy-to-use interface that makes it simple to acquire, set-up and manage virtual machines for doing analyses.

Monthly news

Meet the new recruits!

Chiara Gallese Nobile

Chiara has joined the data steward team at TU Eindhoven as an IT and privacy specialist. After completing her PhD in Japanese Private International Law at [Ca' Foscari University of Venice](#), she has dedicated her research career to law, technology, AI ethics and GDPR, and has worked as a privacy consultant for multinational companies.

Phuong Truong

Phuong completed her PhD in Geoscience at [Wageningen University \(WUR\)](#) and started her position as a data steward at TU Eindhoven earlier this month. She is particularly interested in the creation of FAIR and reproducible code, and participating in the [Software Carpentries!](#)

Floor Luub

After studying a Professional Doctorate in Engineering at TU Eindhoven, **Floor** is excited to assist researchers with their data management as the new data steward in the [Department of Mathematics and Computer Science](#) at TU/e.

New members

Events

What happened in February?... Our highlights of the month!

- The **National Open Science Festival** took place on 11th February... [Read our blog](#) and watch the recorded livestream!
- **Data Sharing and Citation: How Societies Can Make a Difference** on 5th February. Watch the recording and register for the series.
- **Barcamp Open Science (#oscibar)** and the **Open Science Conference (#OSC2021)** from 16th to 19th. Read the [collaborative notes](#).

Event highlights

Dates for your diary...

For upcoming events check out the [Open Research Calendar!](#)

- **Making Dark Data FAIR** event: Data, Society, and Open Science II: Roundtable on the FAIR principles and data-driven scientific practice on **1st March** - [Register](#).
- **Open Research: A Vision for the Future** on **2nd March** - See the [conference booklet](#) and register.
- **FAIRsFAIR National Roadshow** offers a FAIR programme in collaboration with LCRDM and DANS on **2nd March** - [Register](#).
- **Software Carpentry Workshop** for 4TU partner institutions (TU Eindhoven, U/Twente and TU Delft) on **16th, 17th, 23rd & 24th March**. [Register](#).
- 'Moving Beyond the Monograph - New and Creative Models of Academic Publication Scholars Should Know About' on **17th March** - [Register](#).
- **Helis FAIR data stewardship course** for researchers, data stewards and others interested in the topic of FAIR data stewardship runs from **17th to 31st March**.
- Software Sustainability Institute's **Collaborations workshop (CW21)** on **30th March to 1st April** - [Register](#).
- SURF Research Week on **13th to 15th April**. Check out the [programme](#) and register.

Upcoming events

Did you see these datasets?

Last month's top downloaded datasets in the 4TU ResearchData repository!

SandT-Pro: Sand Transport Process measurements under Breaking and Irregular Waves

Author(s): Joep van der Zander, Jan Ribberink, Tom O'Donoghue, Dominic van der A, David Hurther, Peter Thorne and Iván Cáceres

Institution: [University of Twente](#)

Categories: [Geology](#), [Physical Geography and Environmental Geoscience](#)

Keywords: 000 Computer science, knowledge & systems, Business Process Intelligence (BPI), IEEE Task Force on Process Mining, real life event logs

[View the dataset](#)

Monthly
Top downloaded!

BPI Challenge 2012

Author(s): Boudewijn van Dongen

Institution: [Eindhoven University of Technology](#)

Categories: [Information Systems](#), [Business and Management](#)

Keywords: 000 Computer science, knowledge & systems, Business Process Intelligence (BPI), IEEE Task Force on Process Mining, real life event log

[Read more about Boudewijn's research and view the dataset](#)

Inventory of RDM policy for a selection of academic publishers and journals in 2016

Author(s): Rutger de Jong, Henk van den Hoogen, Fieke Schoots, Mariëtte van Selm and [Madeleine de Smaele](#)

Institution: [Delft University of Technology](#), UKB Working Group Research Data

Categories: Library and Information Studies, Policy and Administration

Keywords: Data policies, Data repositories, Data sharing, Journal publishers, Research data

NEW! Data in the spotlight

4TU.ResearchData @4TUResearchData · Apr 1

Your daily dose!

#Data from @UTwente #PhD student Luca Marotta on...

Physical fatigue detection after running around an athletic track!

If you're interested in #Biomedical #Engineering, #Human #Movement & #Sports #Science, check out [bit.ly/fatiguedetecti...](#)

Read more about Daniela's research

Check out her SPACERGY data

Give her research data a retweet! (edited)

Daniela 1.png

twitter APP | 8:50 AM

<https://twitter.com/4TUResearchData/status/1384776416324096000>

4TU.ResearchData @4TUResearchData

Your daily dose!

#Data from @bazilinsky from @tudelft3mE

What driving style makes pedestrians think a passing vehicle is driving automatically?

<https://t.co/HuqOz3tblg>

#automateddriving #automotiveengineering #pedestrians #automaticcar

<https://t.co/OgeGjDqolE>

Show less

Twitter Today at 8:50 AM (402 kB)

<https://pbs.twimg.com/media/EzaHP5fXEANMMr.png> (296 kB)

Weekly
Most recent!

4TU.ResearchData @4TUResearchData · 14 Apr

Your daily dose!

#Data & #Rcode from Prof. Ding from @EEMCS_TUD & Southeast University.

Adaptive simulated inner voice on user's eye-gaze behaviour, perception & judgement in #virtualreality.

#Eye-tracking #Eye-gaze #VirtualCognitions

bit.ly/eyegazedata

twitter APP | 8:50 AM

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4TU.ResearchData @4TUResearchData

Your daily dose!

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Show less

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FAIR Data Fund

FAIR DATA FUND SPRING CALL 2021: MEET THE GRANTEES

Connie Clare
May 15, 2021

0 Comments

CLAUDIU FORGACI

Assistant Professor in **Urban Design** at **Delft University of Technology**
[@claudiuforgaci](#)

Claudiu is engaged in understanding how spatial urbanisation patterns, at multiple spatial and temporal scales, are related to social-ecological resilience in cities.

With the help of the FAIR Data Fund, Claudiu aims to make the qualitative and quantitative findings of the **I-SURF project**, as well as its urban design-driven research methodology, available to the wider community of researchers and practitioners. The data management pipeline will be documented in detail to make sure that the data, workflows and code are FAIR.

- 4TU partner organisations
- €3.500 budget (Spring and Autumn)
- Prepare data for publication

- **Eligible refinement efforts:**
- Implementing metadata standards
- Adding documentation to dataset
- Anonymisation or aggregation
- Proprietary to open data format
- Creating visualisations or materials to improve reusability of data
- Promotion of FAIR dataset at event

Want to learn more?

- Join our community → <https://community.data.4tu.nl/>
- Subscribe to our newsletter → bit.ly/newsletter4TU

Thank you for your attention!